

Managing the Challenges of Climate Change through Mass Media for Sustainable Development in Kogi State

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ABSTRACT

This study is an exploration of the potential of mass media in managing the challenges of climate change in Kogi State. Arguably, climate change has exposed both human beings and their environment to different forms of vulnerability over the years. Some of the major negative impacts of climate change on the human environment include erosion, decline in organic matter, soil biodiversity loss, landslides, desertification and flooding. By extension, the aforementioned impacts of climate change have serious implications on human lives, health and sustainable development. On the other hand, the causes of climate change are all linked to unfriendly interactions of man with his environment. Hence, the need to use feasible tools to communicate the causes and harmful impacts of climate change is necessary. However, mass media such as broadcasting, publishing, and the new media have proved to be effective and steadfast means of communication globally. It is based on this backdrop that this research is undertaken. The work employed the focus group discussion approach of the qualitative research methodology to collect its data using selected respondents within the Ankpa and Omala Local Government Areas of Kogi State. The data was content-analysed, and the results revealed, among other things, that climate change remains one of the factors militating against the economic development of the state. It was also revealed that mass media has the potential to create massive awareness on the causes and impacts of climate change in the state. Thus, the work recommends that the aforesaid means should be employed to communicate the challenges for sustainable development.

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1.1. Introduction

Over the ages, the world has been confronted with different challenges. Some of these challenges are global warming and its implications, which include natural disasters like flooding, changes in rainfall, droughts, and excessive heat, among other cases. The implications of the aforementioned problems on human health and economic development are numerous. Within this context, it has been observed that "health and the environment are inextricably linked. The Lancet recently called climate change the largest global health threat of the 21st century" (Morfeld et al, 2022). This is correct because climate change has created a number of health issues ranging from respiratory issues, heart diseases, pest-related illnesses, water and food-related diseases, which have claimed many lives and are still posing serious threat to human existence.

According to Morfeld et al. (2023), The World Health Organisation (WHO) estimates climate change will cause an additional 250,000 deaths per year between 2030 and 2050 from malnutrition, malaria, diarrhoea, and heat stress alone. Additionally, the direct cost to the health sector could reach \$4 billion per year, with 80% of the cost being shouldered by Sub-Saharan Africa. The unfortunate reality is that low-and middle-income countries experience a higher proportion of adverse health effects from increasing climate variability despite their minimal contributions to global greenhouse emissions.

On the other hand, climate change has remained one of the major obstacles to economic development in recent times. Apart from the loss of a huge amount of properties during natural disasters like flooding, among others, climate change has affected the agricultural activities of many nations of the world. In other words, agricultural activities, which formed the major sources of food production and, by extension, important organs of economic activities of many nations of the world, have been affected by climate change in recent years. Omojebi and Sulieman (2021) noted that, Food insecurity is the single greatest danger of climate change to vulnerable human populations and indeed to all humanity. That is because there are multiple adverse impacts of global warming and climate disruption on agriculture, and all of these impacts will increase as the global temperature increases. Climate-related threats to global food production include risks to grain, vegetable, and fruit crops, livestock, and fisheries.

Indeed, climate change has serious negative impacts on the economic development and overall well-being of the human race. However, it is important to acknowledge the fact that human activities such as indiscriminate bush burning, solid mineral exploration, industrialisation, and deforestation, among others, are some of the major causes of climate change. Similarly, a number of people, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria, have little knowledge about this fact. Based on this backdrop, many means have been used over the years to communicate the knowledge about the causes and dangers of global warming around the world. Mass media seems to be one of such means. In other words, mass media seem to be one of the major and fast-growing means of communication today. One of its advantages lies in the fact that it can spread "information to a number of receivers in customised ways, depending on specification for endorsed categories" (Aboh, 2024). It is based on this that the research is undertaken. The work focuses on the need to share the knowledge of climate change through mass media for a sustainable fight against climate crises for sustainable development.

Literature Review

Concept of Climate Change

Naturally, the world is meant to be green and natural. In other words, the planet was created green with rich soil, forest, vegetation, rivers and valleys. This natural setting was made to sustain a good and better ecosystem and the preservation of all human beings' lives. But over the decades, human beings have been engaged in environmentally harmful practices such as deforestation, bush burning, indiscriminate dumping of waste materials, and exploration of mineral resources. These activities in

one way or another have tampered with the natural world and thereby created crises for the climatic conditions of the globe.

According to Ayo et al. (2023), Climate encompasses the statistics of temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind, precipitation, atmospheric particle count and other meteorological elemental measurements in a given region over long periods of time. Climate change is the drastic alteration in natural components of the atmospheric environment, with the resultant adverse responses such as the shift in weather variations or patterns involving overall and unprecedented changes in weather patterns, which may include unusual rain yield or precipitation temperature, density or cloud look.

Many reasons are said to be responsible for climate change. Apart from natural causes like oceanic circulation, biotic processes, variation in solar radiation received by earth, plate tectonics and volcanic eruptions, and human-induced alteration of the natural world like exploration, deforestation, bush burning, among many others, have equally been identified as one of the factors contributing to the challenges of global warming. Thus, Ayo et al. (2019) support that the public has also been blamed for their contribution to climate change, which is affecting Food Security in Nigeria. In the bid to meet our energy needs, Nigerians over-depend on the use of fossil fuels, which leads to the release of toxic gases like greenhouse gases (GHGs), mainly carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane, into the atmosphere. Fertilisers used in our farms to improve crop yield are also petrochemical products, which also affect the atmosphere negatively. Excess fertiliser escapes from fields as gases into the atmosphere. The use of synthetic nitrogen fertiliser has accelerated the increase in nitrous oxide in the last few decades.

Indeed, global warming has serious consequences for humans. It affects the natural ecosystem and rainfall changes, which, by extension, lead to drought, desertification and flooding. All these have threatened human health and economic activities such as agricultural production, among other things, over the years.

Conceptualising Mass Media

The term Mass Media has enjoyed a lot of reviews over the years. A number of scholars have looked at it based on its history, forms, features and functions. However, in a way of a simple description, mass media can be seen as the medium of communication employed to convey information to large numbers of people simultaneously. Some of the media of mass media are books, newspapers, magazines, film, radio, television, audio and music recordings, and the internet. In recent times, the internet has served as the major and widely used form of mass media, followed by television and radio. The internet arm of the mass media is often referred to as New Media.

The New Media refers to a type of media that is digital and interactive in nature. Historically, Redeem Token in Zhang (2020) says that, "the first recognisable social media site, Six Degrees, was created in 1997. It enabled users to upload a profile and make friends with other users. In 1999, the first blogging sites became popular, creating a social media sensation that's still popular today". Today, there are different forms of new media platforms. Notable among them are blogs, mobile apps, social media networks, streaming services, virtual and augmented reality, and websites, among others. It is important to note that new media has its unique characteristics. It is digital,

virtual, interactive, simulated and globally networked; its multiple attributes give it the qualities of a multi-media, which makes it have more advantages over traditional media. Perhaps, these formed the bases for its appreciations among other forms of mass media by a number of scholars over the years.

According to Zhang (2023), the traditional media communication is one-way; TV programs and films will go through a long process from production to the program broadcast, during which period the audience is isolated. The audience needs to find a new platform if they want to give feedback. In this one-way communication mode, it is difficult to get feedback from the audience; their discourse is deprived to a certain extent. But in the new media short video platform, the communication is multi-directional and open. Traditional television communicates through television channels, and the audience must choose a program by changing the channel. They can only passively watch according to the program schedule formulated by the television station. TikTok is based on mobile phones; people are able to watch the videos anytime and anywhere using their phones.

Zhang further argues that, also, with the support of network traffic technology, the short video platform has the characteristic of 'immediacy', the publisher can receive the user's feedback on the content for the first time after publishing (2023). Beyond this, all new media channels are interlinked. This simply means that none of the platforms is an independent app; content can be shared from one of the platforms to others with ease. Through this, an online community where different issues can be shared among large numbers of friends can be established.

Concept of Development

The concept of development is the result of the growing awareness of the global links between mounting environmental problems, socio-economic issues related to poverty and inequality and concerns about a healthy future for humanity. It strongly links environmental and socio-economic issues. The first important use of the term was in 1980 in the World Conservation Strategy (IUCN et al, 2018).

This process of bringing together environmental and socio-economic questions was most famously expressed in the Brundtland Report's (2021) sees development as meeting "the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs" This defines needs from a human standpoint; as Lee (2022) has argued, sustainable development is an unashamedly anthropocentric concept.

Brundtland's definition and the ideas expressed in the report Our Common Future, recognise the dependency of humans on the environment to meet needs and well-being in a much wider sense than merely exploiting resources, "ecology and economy are becoming ever more interwoven – locally, regionally, nationally and globally" (Griffith and Inniss, 1992). Rather than domination over nature, our lives, activities and society are nested within the environment (Giddings et al, 2002). The report stresses that humanity, whether in an industrialised or a rural subsistence society, depends for security and basic existence on the environment, the economy and our well-being now and in the future.

Perhaps the above is the reason the United Nations (UN)'s report (2020) says that sustainable development is the organising principle for meeting human development goals, while at the same time sustaining the ability of natural systems to provide the natural resources and ecosystem services upon which the economy and society depend. The desirable end result of this is a state of society where living conditions and resource use continue to meet human needs without undermining the integrity and stability of the natural systems. Sustainable development is that development that meets our present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

According to the United Nations' report (2021), the components that work together to produce sustainable development are economic development, social development and environmental protection. These three must be conceptualised together, planned together and implemented together by a government to achieve the desired results. So, sustainable development in a way has a moral dimension that demands a great sense of responsibility from the leader (government) and the follower (citizen).

Furthermore, the social and economic development process in society is regarded as socio-economic development. Indicators such as life expectancy, GDP, employment levels and literacy levels are human development index (HDI) indicators used for its measurement. Also considered are changes in factors that are less tangible, such as personal dignity, personal safety, freedom of association, freedom from physical harm or fear and the civic participation of the people. Factors that cause socio-economic impacts include changes in law, technologies, ecological changes and changes in the physical environment (Mac Ewan and Arthur, 2024).

Development that is said to be Socio-economic is a process that identifies both the economic and social needs of the community. It seeks to draft a strategic plan that will address identified needs in practical ways and in the best interest of the community over a long period of time. The main idea is to discover how to enhance the living standard of the people living within the area and, at the same time, ensure that economic activity is capable of sustaining the people (Lechner, 2021).

Socio-economic development is an important concept pertaining to the problem of change in the socio-economic sphere. Environmental changes taking place in the socio sphere are embraced by socio-economic development. Despite the fact that the economic aspect comes to the fore in carrying out studies on the changes in the economy, they, however, cannot be isolated from the social aspect. "It protects its functioning in connection with the economic aspects of a society's life. This branch of economic theory has its primary interest in the types of socio-economic systems, ownership relations and interest and also the motivation behind economic activity. Defining socio-economic development as a chain of changes has to do with identifying what are the features of those changes and what are their determinants.

This, therefore, means that we need to know what could be counted as socio-economic development. In order to represent the exact features of socio-economic development, we are implored to identify the nature of the process and goals of changes that are part of this type of process or/and/or developmental agenda. This process, generally, is an

ordered sequence of changes in the state of affairs, where a certain state decides the other states that will follow it. Its dynamic component is structured to achieve its target.

Theoretical Framework

This work is underpinned by Attention Economy Theory. The theory was propounded by Herbert Simon in 1958. It proposes that human beings are naturally attention seekers and givers. Hence, one of the major goals of any communication channel is to capture the attention of the audience. In this context, for a communication channel to achieve its aim, it must be able to sustain the audience's limited attention. The theory argues that people's attention is a valuable resource and that communication channels should compete for it. It states that, as people are selective of what they pay attention to, ways to engage their attention successfully should be constantly sought. This research focuses on the need to explore the potential of mass media to direct the attention of people towards issues of climate crises for sustainable development.

Apparently, this theory has bearings with the thrust of this study. The advantage of mass media in its large capacity, interactivity, and real-time communication compared to traditional media has made it capture the attention of people over the years. Thus, through it, information about the dangers and how to manage the abovementioned challenges could be disseminated for a sustainable fight against global warming and a sustainable environment.

1.2. Results and Discussion

Climate Change in Kogi State: The Roles of Mass Media in Managing the Menace

In order to realise the aim and objectives of the study, the researcher employed the focus group discussion approach of the qualitative research methodology. Through this approach, reliable and unbiased data were collected from respondents who include media experts, meteorologists, farmers, economists and development analysts, among others, within the study area.

One of the discussants, Idish Abubakar (Focus Group Discussion, Ankpa L.G.A, 23/12/2025), says that, like the other parts of the world, climate crises have been one of the major threats to the lives and economic prosperity of the people of Kogi state. For instance, climate change has resulted in ecological issues such as erosion in many parts of the state. This has not only affected human health, urban planning and development, but it has also negatively impacted the agricultural activities of the people.

Lawal Yusuf (Focus Group Discussion, Omala L.G.A, 26/12/2025), on the other hand, stated that climate crises have greatly impacted the major economic activity of the people, which is agriculture. In Omala Local Government Area of the state, cashew is one of the major agricultural products of the people. In recent years, this agricultural product has witnessed a serious decrease due to climate-related challenges.

In the same vein, reports of how houses, people and properties have been washed away by flood in many parts of the state, especially its river-bank areas like Lokoja, Ibaji, Idah, Itobe and Bagana are not news. Beyond this, the flood has on many occasions exposed the people to water-borne diseases, claiming lives and causing financial burden for the government (Seidu Yhaya, Focus Group Discussion, Ankpa L.G.A, 23/12/2025).

The above positions seem to agree with Joseph's (2023) study, which noted that climate change and variability pose serious risks to rain-fed agricultural land use in the semi-dry agro-ecological zones of Nigeria. Kogi State is not an exception. Rainfall is becoming more unpredictable and unreliable both in its timing and its volume, and growing seasons are changing, and ecological zones are shifting.

When the discussants were asked about the potential of mass media in managing the issues of climate crises in the state, Zanab Aminu (Focus Group Discussion, Ankpa L.G.A, 23/12/2025), argued that the majority of the people have little or no knowledge about the causes and harmful impacts of climate change. Beyond the various mineral resources exploration operations going on in the state, which have huge implications on the environment, the people are also ignorant of the fact that burning fossil fuels, cutting down forests, farming livestock, and careless dumping of waste materials can influence the climate and the earth's temperature. Many of our people can learn about this information through the mass media.

In addition, Musa Shehu (Focus Group Discussion, Ankpa L.G.A, 23/12/2025), supported that one of the best ways society could be educated on any burning social issues today is through mass media. People use each of its channels; radio, television, books and newspapers on a daily basis; and it covers large audiences, and some of them get to the users at a very fast rate. Hence, the causes and implications of climate change in Kogi state can be best disseminated through mass media.

Roseline Idachaba (Focus Group Discussion, Omala L.G.A, 26/12/2025) added that climate change has serious implications for both human and sustainable development. Mass media is an important instrument that can be used to control climate change-related challenges. Mass media is a strong part of human society in today's world. Apart from the mass media channels like television and radio, new media platforms of different forms are used by people of different ages today as their means of communication.

Based on the abovementioned, sharing of information about climate crises through new media could be a better option. The new media is a fundamental factor in bringing the world into a smaller community. According to McLuhan (2022), the new media is "an instant implosion" that reverses the specialism of the print age and contracts the globe to a village in which everybody lives in the utmost proximity created by our electric involvement in one another's lives. Hence, as has been mentioned, the distribution of knowledge about the causes and dangers of climate change through new media is very important in the global fight against the climate crisis.

1.3. Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the data analysis and findings of research, the climate crisis remains one of the major challenges confronting the globe. It has impacted negatively on human health and the economic development of the world. A number of hideous human activities, such as poor waste management practices, industrialisation, deforestation, bush burning, and solid mineral exploration, among others, have been identified as contributing factors to the challenges of global warming. Thus, the need to address the challenges through potent instruments like mass media is sacrosanct.

In line with the findings of the study, the work recommends that:

1. People should be encouraged to maintain the natural environment at all costs. In this context, harmful activities like bush burning, deforestation and careless dumping of waste materials should be avoided.
2. Secondly, mass media channels such as radio and television should strengthen their efforts in disseminating climate change information.
3. In the same vein, the various new media platforms should be employed in communicating climate crisis messages to the people.
4. More so, scholars should not be left out of the ongoing discussion on the dangers and impacts of climate change.

1.4. References

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Appendix: FGD Discussants

S/N	Name	Age	Sex	Occupation	Background	Location
1	Abutu Gowon	35	Male	Civil servant	Educated	Idah
2	Atanu Lawrence	28	Male	Civil servant	Educated	Idah
3	Adama Amade	45	Male	Civil servant	Educated	Dekina
4	Onugu W.S	46	Male	Civil servant	Educated	Dekina
5	Okpanachi Jonathan	48	Male	Civil servant	Educated	Dekina
6	Marriam Sule	34	Female	Farmer	Educated	Idah